

Novel X-ray imaging techniques for the noninvasive investigation of European Heritage within MOLAB platform of E-RIHS

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The MOLAB platform of E-RIHS, the European Infrastructure for Heritage Science, provides access to advanced analytical spectroscopies for the non-invasive characterization of tangible cultural heritage on site. XRAYLab of the Institute of Heritage Science (ISPC-CNR) in Catania specializes in developing novel mobile X-ray instruments for use in MOLAB's collaborative projects. Since 2021, the laboratory has conducted more than 20 measurement campaigns to study heritage objects selected through the competitive calls of ERIHS for access through the MOLAB. Among the investigated materials, painted artworks represent a significant focus for the heritage science community. The analytical capabilities of advanced X-ray technologies developed by the XRAYLab have allowed for better elucidation of pigment materials, creative processes and conservation states of iconic masterpieces such the hunting frieze of the Philip II tomb in Vergina (Greece), the 16m long Book of Death of the funerary tomb of Kha and Merit at the Museo Egizio in Torino, and the frescoes by Masolino, Masaccio and Lippi at the Brancacci chapel in Florence.

In the measurement activities performed, we have combined on the same object different analytical techniques to investigate both the chemical nature of the painted materials and their layered structure. A highly sensitive MA-XRF scanner with on-the-fly imaging capabilities, a strongly focused beam and 6-SDDs detection device, provides the elemental distribution images of the paintings that are crucial to understand the nature of the pigments and the modus operandi of the artist. A novel MA-XRPD based on linear Si-strip detectors covering the Bragg region is then applied for obtaining pigment specific identification and to highlight their related degradation products. Finally, we recently introduced a mobile high-resolution digital radiography equipped with a motorized frame, a flat panel covering 54x40cm² area with 120mm pixel pitch, and a 1kW X-ray source that allows the in-situ investigation of panels and canvas painting with dimensions up to 200x180cm². In this work, we present the experimental details of the device used during the MOLAB activities and some compelling results.